

PREVALENCE AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CUTANEOUS LEISHMANIASIS IN TEHSIL MAMUND, BAJAUR AGENCY, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a vector-borne parasitic disease caused by protozoa of the genus *Leishmania*. In Pakistan, it is commonly reported from Baluchistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Punjab, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK), and the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA). This study aimed to determine the prevalence and epidemiological characteristics of CL in Tehsil Wara and Tehsil Lowy Mamaund of Bajaur Agency.

Methods: In a descriptive cross-sectional study, 207 clinically suspected CL cases from the community and basic health units were examined. Convenience sampling was used. After obtaining informed consent, demographic and clinical data (age, sex, lesion number, type, and site) were recorded. Smears from lesion margins were prepared, fixed with methanol, stained with Giemsa, and examined microscopically for amastigotes.

Results: Of 207 suspected cases, 134 (64.73%) were confirmed positive. Prevalence was higher in females (68.30%, n=86/126) than in males (59.26%, n=48/81). The highest infection rate was in the 1-10 years age group (44.93%). The face was the most common lesion site (82.6%, n=171). Most patients had a single lesion (81.2%, n=168), and the wet type of lesion was predominant (93.71%, n=194).

Conclusion: Cutaneous leishmaniasis remains a significant public health problem in the study area, disproportionately affecting young children and females. Community awareness and vector control measures are urgently needed.

Keywords: Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, Prevalence, Epidemiology.

INTRODUCTION

Cutaneous leishmaniasis (CL), alongside visceral (VL) and mucocutaneous (MCL) forms, is a parasitic disease caused by flagellate protozoa of the genus *Leishmania* and transmitted by female phlebotomine sand flies. It is a widespread disease in tropical and subtropical regions [1]. The disease represents a significant global burden, affecting an

estimated 0.7 to 1.3 million people annually worldwide, with the Middle East and Central Asia contributing a substantial proportion of cases [2]. The clinical spectrum begins when promastigotes are inoculated into the skin during a sand fly bite, where they are phagocytosed and transform into amastigotes within macrophages, leading to

localized cutaneous pathology [3]. The classic presentation is a skin ulcer on exposed body parts like the face, hands, or legs, which can heal spontaneously but often results in disfiguring scars, causing significant social stigma [4].

In Pakistan, CL is endemic, with both zoonotic and anthroponotic cycles reported, and an estimated 21,000 to 35,000 cases occur annually [5]. *Leishmania tropica* is considered the primary causative agent [6]. The disease has expanded its geographical distribution in recent years and is commonly reported from Baluchistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Punjab, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK), and the Federally Administered Tribal Areas [5][7]. Within KPK and FATA, areas like Swat, Dir, and the tribal agencies are known endemic foci [8]. Diagnosis in resource-limited settings often relies on clinical suspicion and microscopic identification of amastigotes in Giemsa-stained lesion smears, a method with reasonable sensitivity. The disease burden is exacerbated by risk factors such as poverty, poor housing, climate change, and population movements [9][4].

The rationale for this study was to determine the prevalence of CL and its epidemiological correlates, including age, sex, lesion number, type, and site in Tehsil Mamund of Bajaur Agency. This region is socio-geographically significant and borders endemic areas of Afghanistan. The study aims to generate localized data to highlight this neglected tropical disease, advocate for the establishment of control programs, and inform public health interventions, given the associated social stigma and the current absence of a national leishmaniasis control strategy.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted, and data were collected from the Community Health Center (CHC) and Basic Health Unit (BHU) of Tehsil Mamund, Bajaur Agency, FATA. A total of 207 clinically suspected CL cases were included via convenience sampling. Inclusion criteria were clinically suspected of active CL lesions, while chronic cases were excluded.

After obtaining informed consent, a Performa was used to record demographic (name, age, sex, residency) and clinical data (lesion site, type, number, duration). For sample collection, the active margin of the lesion was cleaned with 70% ethyl alcohol, pressed, and punctured with a sterile lancet. The expressed fluid was smeared onto a clean glass slide, air-dried, and fixed with 100% methanol for 1-2 minutes. Slides were stained with Giemsa stain for 10-15 minutes, washed, dried, and examined under a light microscope using oil immersion (100x objective). Amastigotes were identified morphologically as round to oval, purple structures, often within macrophages. The data were analyzed through PSSS version 27, and data were presented in tabulated and graphical form.

Results

Overall Prevalence and Gender Distribution

Out of 207 suspected cases, 134 (64.73%) were positive for CL. Females constituted 60.9% (n=126) of the sample, with a positivity rate of 68.30% (n=86). Males constituted 39.1% (n=81), with a positivity rate of 59.26% (n=48) (Table 1).

Table 1: Gender-wise distribution of CL cases

Gender	Positive Cases	Percentage	Negative Cases	Percentage	Total
Male	48	59.26%	33	40.74%	81
Female	86	68.30%	40	31.70%	126
Total	134	64.73%	73	35.27%	207

Tehsil-wise Distribution

Prevalence was higher in Tehsil Wara (59.43%, n=123) than in Tehsil Lowy Mamund (40.57%, n=84). Female cases outnumbered male cases in both tehsils Table 2.

Table 2: Tehsil-wise distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis

Tehsil	Male	Females	Total	Percentages
Loi	30	54	84	40.57%
Wara	51	72	123	59.43
Total	81	126	207	100%

Age-wise Distribution

The highest prevalence was in the 1-10-year-old age group (44.93%), with infection rates declining with increasing age fig. 1.

Figure 1: Age-wise distribution of cutaneous leishmaniasis

Lesion Site: The face was the most affected site (82.6%, n=171), followed by hands (10.14%, n=21), legs and feet (5.8%, n=12), and other sites (1.45%, n=3) fig. 2.

Figure 2: Common lesions noted in patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis

Number and Type of Lesions

Most patients (81.2%, n=168) had a single lesion. Two lesions were found in 18.3% (n=38) and three lesions in 0.5% (n=1) of patients. The wet type of lesion was overwhelmingly predominant (93.71%, n=194) compared to the dry type (6.28%, n=13).

Table 3: Frequency of the number of lesions in patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis

No. lesions	No. of patients	Percentage
1 lesion	168	81.2%
2 lesions	38	18.3%
3 lesions	1	0.5%
Total	207	100%

Discussion

The prevalence of CL in Tehsil Mamund (64.73%) is slightly higher than the rates reported in the study [10]. Our finding of a higher proportional burden in Bajaur district (64.73%) compared to the previous study [11] in the preceding period may reflect an ongoing escalation of the epidemic in this region. This trend underscores the persistent and worsening nature of the risk factors specific to Bajaur.

The higher prevalence in females (68.30%) contrasts with the study [10]. This disparity may be due to greater and more consistent exposure of females in the study area, as they are often engaged in agricultural work, animal husbandry, and collecting wood or straw outdoors, particularly at dawn and dusk when sand flies are most active. Furthermore, housing conditions in the region may not provide adequate protection against indoor sand fly bites, disproportionately exposing women and children. The highest infection burden in children aged 1-10 years aligns with their increased outdoor activity, lesser use of protective clothing, and possibly developing immune systems, making them more vulnerable to sand fly bites and primary infections [12].

The observed predominance of facial lesions (82.6%) is a consistent and concerning finding across endemic regions [13], as it directly contributes to the psychological burden and social stigma associated with CL due to scarring. The fact that most patients (81.2%) presented with a single lesion is typical for classic localized CL. The overwhelming majority of wet-type lesions (93.71%) in our study aligns with findings by Sami et al [13], but contrasts with other reports

associating *L. tropica* (considered the main agent in Pakistan) with dry, crusted lesions [14]. This suggests the possible co-circulation of *Leishmania major* in the region, which is classically associated with moist, exudative lesions [15], or could indicate variant clinical presentations of *L. tropica* influenced by host immune responses. A key limitation of this study was the inability to perform species identification via PCR or culture, which is necessary for definitive species-level diagnosis, understanding local transmission dynamics (zoonotic vs. anthroponotic), and guiding appropriate clinical and public health responses.

Conclusion

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is a major and persistent public health challenge in Tehsil Mamund, Bajaur Agency, with high prevalence among young children and females. The findings underscore the need for targeted interventions.

Recommendations

To reduce CL transmission, integrated strategies are recommended: community health education on personal protection (use of bed nets, insecticide sprays, wearing long-sleeved clothing), improvement in sanitation and waste management to reduce sand fly breeding sites, and implementation of active surveillance and vector control programs. Future studies should incorporate molecular techniques for species identification to guide specific control measures.

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